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The Emergence And Development of Social Organisation in Baykan Sezer Sociology

Baykan Sezer'in Sosyolojisinde Sosyal Örgütlenmenin Ortaya Çıkışı ve Gelişimi

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Abstract

The structure we define as "society", which is the subject of sociology and in which we all live, is also a form of social organization. The birth/emergence of society or a form of social organization is not sufficiently discussed in the social sciences. This leads to the impression that society is a given, absolute form of organization that automatically and spontaneously emerges from nature. However, the form of social organization is not given and absolute. It emerged at a certain stage of human history. In this paper, the birth and development of societies or forms of social organization will be discussed and the main factor that determines social change will be emphasized.

Keywords: Baykan Sezer, Sezer Sosyolojisi, The Formation of Societies, Form of Social Organization

Özet

Sosyolojinin konusu olan ve hepimizin içinde yaşadığı "toplum" olarak tanımladığımız yapı da bir sosyal örgütlenme biçimidir. Toplumun veya bir sosyal örgütlenme biçiminin doğuşu/ortaya çıkışı sosyal bilimlerde yeterince tartışılmamaktadır. Bu durum, toplumun doğadan otomatik ve kendiliğinden ortaya çıkan, verilmiş, mutlak bir örgütlenme biçimi olduğu izlenimine yol açmaktadır. Ancak, sosyal örgütlenme biçimi verilmiş ve mutlak değildir. İnsanlık tarihinin belirli bir aşamasında ortaya çıkmıştır. Bu makalede, toplumların veya sosyal örgütlenme biçimlerinin doğuşu ve gelişimi tartışılacak ve sosyal değişimi belirleyen temel faktör vurgulanacaktır.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Baykan Sezer, Sezer Sosyolojisi, Toplumların Oluşumu, Toplumsal Örgütlenme Biçimi

1. Introduction

The most basic and general model of forms of organisation is the form of social organisation. This first and most important form of organisation can be traced back to the transition to social life. In this case, it is necessary to start discussing the topic with the society itself and to address the conditions of development of society and, accordingly, of

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communication. Only then will it be possible to trace organizations in history and provide a fundamental explanation of the subject rather than explaining communication according to today's conditions and its current appearance?

Here, it is important to mention that the source of our discussions on society is Baykan Sezer's work titled "Societies in History"[1]. The assumption that will be put forward below is based on Sezer's approach. The basic assumption is that society is not an absolute, pre-given, automatic, natural form of organization. On the contrary, social life or social organization has emerged later as a form of solution developed by human beings in order to overcome the problems they face.

In other words, social life is a stage in the development of humanity. The fact that social life goes back to the beginning of humanity gives the impression that this form of organization is absolute and given. The fact that this form of organization has been observed since the beginning of history does not make it an absolute event that happens automatically; on the contrary, it means that people could not solve the problems they encountered in their first relations on their own and that they found the solution in the transition to social life.

2. Foundations of Social Organisation

In the beginning, human beings interact with nature in order to solve their basic problems of survival, protection and sustenance. In the face of these initial and basic problems, humans do not have a spontaneous solution through direct and immediate relations. This makes a constant and compulsory relationship with nature a necessity. However, the fact that human beings do not have sufficient and necessary equipment in this relationship with nature will lead to problems. Human beings are perhaps the weakest of beings alive in terms of their natural endowment. Therefore, a total harmony with nature is out of the question. Animals find spontaneous and instant solutions in their relations with nature because of the harmony between their natural structures - their teeth, claws, skin, etc. - and the laws of nature [2]. Thus, animals are able to establish a harmonious relationship with nature thanks to their innate equipment. Humans cannot achieve the same harmony through direct relationships and solve their problems automatically. The inability to solve their problems through heredity or instinct, through spontaneous and immediate relations, will pave the way for them to develop other and indirect relations and to find solutions within these relations.

A solution resulting from a lack of equipment and natural weakness, and realized through the development of an indirect type of relationship other than a direct one, will not only give human beings a very important superiority among other living beings, but will also lead to the transition to social life. Social life is far from being a product of nature. Social life is the solution humans bring against nature. As a result, social life has been widespread throughout humanity, but with great variation and diversity. If social life were a natural and automatic phenomenon, all societies on earth would have the same characteristics. The differences between societies in Africa and Europe cannot be explained by differences in the nature of African and European people. It is the differences in the problems encountered and the solutions found to these problems through the means available under the circumstances that can explain the differences. While the relationship with nature is the only possible relationship in the beginning, the fact that the problems encountered here cannot be overcome by spontaneous and direct relationships will lead to an enrichment and diversity in human relationships. Human-nature relations will no longer be limited to the human-nature relationship, and since the problems cannot be solved through these relations, inter-human [3] and then inter-societal relations [4] will come to the fore.

The relationship between people will show different characteristics than the human-nature relationship. Humans are not passive like nature. Therefore, communication is necessary in maintaining a healthy relationship. The necessity of exchanging information and news between the parties that emerged with the beginning of the relationship between people will lead to the birth of communication. With the positive results of interpersonal relations, the solution of transition to community life has been reached. Certain characteristics of this solution, this form of organization, will prepare the social foundations of communication.

First of all, this solution cannot be realized through individual relations, but requires a collective effort [5]. A structuring and division of labor is required during this organizational stage. And it is on this point that the social basis of communication rests. In the transition to social life, the organization of relations and efforts and their orientation towards a certain goal will only be possible through communication to be established during the effort. Communication will not only be a necessity in organizing relations and directing them towards a certain goal during the transition to social life, but it will also make it possible to ensure unity and harmony within society. The problem of achieving unity and harmony and creating a community identity is not limited to the members of the community. As society develops and becomes more complex, different social institutions will emerge in response to various needs. To ensure the unity

and relations between these institutions and to ensure the continuity of society, communication systems embodied in the form of an organized social institution will come to the fore.

In addition, people need to be organized according to these new relations, the solution that these relations give rise to and the characteristics of this solution. Especially due to the limitations of the solution reached at the beginning, it is inevitable that those who will participate in and benefit from the solution will also be limited. It is obviously not possible to think that in the first examples of social life, very large-scale social unions were formed. Therefore, in addition to the limitations of participation in the solution, this participation will also need to be organized. (Even today, societies that do not want to share their total opportunities and blessings with “others” other than their own members take a series of measures, starting with visas, to prevent foreigners from easily entering their countries.)

None of these solutions and necessities will happen by itself. Those who participate in the solution and those who benefit from it have to communicate among themselves in order to become partners in the non-spontaneous solution. This necessity is the first aspect of the connection between communication and community life. The foregoing relates to the first dimension of communication, communication in the field. Today, newspapers, radio, television, telephone, internet are the means of communication in the field.

However, there is a second very important dimension of communication that is not addressed in research and theories, and this is intergenerational communication, which shows the time dimension of communication. We have already explained that as a single individual, human beings cannot solve their problems through the immediate and direct relationships they establish, but they can only overcome their problems by organizing themselves as a society. This non-automatic, non-spontaneous solution will require certain necessities.

Foremost among these necessities is the need to learn this non-automatic solution. Since it does not happen automatically and spontaneously, the repetition of the solution in question will only be possible through learning [6]. It is precisely at this point that the second aspect of the connection between communication and society emerges. We have already mentioned that the absence of spontaneous, immediate relationships developed by people at the source of all the problems and solutions developed, except for the first problems in the face of nature, i.e. the non-automatic nature of this solution, necessitates that solutions must be learned and transmitted. This necessity requires a transfer not only at that time, but also between generations. One of the most important institutes in intergenerational communication is education. Communication within the framework of transferring the solution, which is not innate and does not happen spontaneously, will not be limited to instant communication between members of society, but will reveal the necessity of intergenerational communication.

Within the various ways and means to be used for intergenerational communication, school and education will be closely related to the solution. For instance, it is no coincidence that writing was used in the Near East, where the first organized and permanent, solid solution emerged, and that the first educational institutions were also found in Sumer. In societies where the first and important developments in the name of civilization took place, the first educational institutions also took their place. The aim of these institutes is the transfer of information about the solution obtained. Therefore education should be included in any endeavour to explain communication.

We have talked about the problems faced and solutions developed. In its shortest form, we mean social, historical development, progress. Societies differ in time as well as in space. And this surfaces through changes and developments societies show. The development and disintegration of societies is also measured by the differences they show over time. Societies have to face new problems over time. Since all these problems require new solutions, a new form of society emerges. There are only a few societies that have survived to the present day by preserving the same structure and therefore all their characteristics.

Although social life brings a solution to the problems encountered, it will also give rise to new and different problems. This way of organization that made it possible for the initial problems to be overcome will create new problems at a higher level. These are new problems that have never been witnessed before. These new problems, in turn, will lead to the development of new relationships and solutions, and thus the achievements made in the face of higher level problems will lead to the progress of societies, that is, social change.

Society tries to overcome the new problems it faces by adapting its own structure to the inter-societal relations. (For example, today, Turkey's the aim of joining the European Union to solve its fundamental problems and the attempt to design society and the way it is organized in accordance with this goal by enacting harmonization laws.) Societies will try to overcome their problems and change by making new arrangements within their own structure and adapting the

way they are organized to these conditions. This is the most fundamental dynamic that enables societies to move forward. Otherwise, if organizing in the form of a society solved some problems, but did not bring new and other problems at a higher level, no society would have changed their original form.

At this point, an important question arises: What is the source of the problems and solutions that determine all this? At the root of both the problems and the solutions developed lies the relationships that societies enter into. The relationships in which societies are involved are the source of their fundamental problems, as well as the determining factors that enable them to generate new solutions.

Placing “relations” at the heart of the issue is not an uncommon form of explanation. Relations within a society are often cited as the source of its problems and the solutions developed in response to them. The most concrete example of this is Marx's theory of class conflict. Marx argues that the basic dynamic that determines social change, and even history, is the relationship/conflict between classes within society. However, the fundamental problems faced by societies and the fundamental solutions they develop should be searched at the level of broader relations.

These relations that shape societies and history are those that happen at the broadest level, between societies, between civilizations. Therefore, it might be argued that the main motivation and character of the way social organization phenomenon derives from the internal dynamics of societies and the social solutions generated by inter-societal (and sometimes inter-civilizational) relations, and therefore technical development in the means of communication is not the dominant element of the phenomenon of communication. Societies will acquire their characteristics according to the solution and the identity, personality, and organizational form of the society based on this solution. For this reason, it is not possible to put forth a uniform type/system of communication in history - at least until a certain period - or a uniform type/system of way of organization in line with today's understanding. Differences in solutions lead to differentiated societies and identities. These relations that shape societies and history are those that happen at the broadest level, between societies, between civilizations. Therefore, it might be argued that the main motivation and character of the way social organization phenomenon derives from the internal dynamics of societies and the social solutions generated by inter-societal (and sometimes inter-civilizational) relations, and therefore technical development in the means of communication is not the dominant element of the phenomenon of communication. Societies will acquire their characteristics according to the solution and the identity, personality, and organizational form of the society based on this solution. For this reason, it is not possible to put forth a uniform type/system of communication in history - at least until a certain period - or a uniform type/system of way of organization in line with today's understanding. Differences in solutions lead to differentiated societies and identities.

In different periods of history, societies have had different forms of organization. Just as there are different features between the ways of organization of imperial organizations and the ways of organization of today's nation-state organizations, or as we encounter very different ways of social organization systems in the West in the Greek, Roman, Middle Ages, and beyond.

3. Conclusion

As can be seen, the most basic and globally widespread form of organization is society. As Baykan Sezer states, it is the position of a society in international relations that gives the form of social organization its characteristics. Societies acquire their identities and personalities, in other words, their most fundamental characteristics, according to their place and role in international and even inter-civilizational relations.

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